

Learning histories, participatory methods and creative engagement for climate resilience

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Abstract

The potential of place-based, historically-informed approaches to drive climate action has not yet been adequately interrogated. Recent scholarly work has focussed on climate communication and the role of arts and humanities-led storytelling in engaging people in climate narratives. Far less has been said about mobilising arts and creativity to build anticipatory climate action. Nor have archival material and pre-twentieth century histories of living with water and flood been widely utilised in this endeavour. This paper reflects on our experiences delivering the UKRI-funded Risky Cities programme and specifically, of developing and utilising a learning histories approach that folds together past, present and future in productive ways so as to learn from the past and the present to rethink the future. Risky Cities uses this approach to develop engagement tools at different scales, evaluating their impact throughout. We find consistently that using learning histories as the foundation of arts-led and creative community engagement makes big narratives about global climate change locally meaningful and relevant. Crucially, this drives anticipatory action and behavioural change in relation to flood risk and resilience. The projects described here underline the effectiveness of place-based, historically-informed creative community engagement for driving cognitive shifts and behavioural change for both participants and audiences. Our learning histories approach can thus be understood as a valuable participatory research method and an effective tool for building climate action, empowerment and resilience.

Introduction

The Risky Cities programme utilises ‘learning histories’ as the foundation of place-based, historically-informed, creative community engagement that offers opportunities to make big global narratives about climate change tangible and relatable at the local level – and so drive anticipatory climate action.¹ In doing so, our work holds in dialogue the pre modern past and as yet uncertain futures, thinking forward through the past to build flood resilience and climate action, with the ambition of shaping new, more inclusive ‘water cultures’ today and for the future. Our work to date has taken place in Kingston-Upon-Hull, UK, a city which has experienced major flooding in recent years – most notably, in June 2007 – and is increasingly vulnerable to flood hazards in the face of future climate change. Yet international recognition of Hull’s flood risk has not translated into strong community engagement on water and flood issues.² Only 6.6% of Hull’s population have signed up to receive Environment Agency Flood Alerts, for example, compared to more than 40 per cent of the population in nearby Doncaster, Harrogate and Barnsley.³ There is an urgent need to work with and better engage community stakeholders in awareness raising and resilient building actions and behaviours.

Recent research shows that site-specific climate arts⁴ and locally-rooted stories of living with water and flood can help make global climate issues meaningful to audiences.⁵ Much of this

¹ E. Brookes, B. McDonagh, C. Wagner, J. Ashton, A. Harvey-Fishenden, N. Macdonald, A. Kennedy-Asser and K. Smith, Learning from arts and heritage-based approaches for building climate resilience in the UK, in: R. Harcourt, S. Dessai, and K. Lonsdale (Eds), *Quantifying Climate Risk and Building Resilience in the UK*, Palgrave Macmillan (2023).

² Hull City Council, *Local Flood Risk Management Strategy 2022—2028*, 13 [https://www.hull.gov.uk/sites/hull/files/media/Editor%20-%20Council%20and%20democracy/Hull%27s Local Flood Risk Management Strategy 2022 - 2028.pdf](https://www.hull.gov.uk/sites/hull/files/media/Editor%20-%20Council%20and%20democracy/Hull%27s%20Local%20Flood%20Risk%20Management%20Strategy%2022%20-%202028.pdf) last accessed 30 March 2023.

³ Hull City Council, Residents urged to register for flood warnings as only 6.6 per cent signed up, <https://www.hullccnews.co.uk/23/06/2022/residents-urged-to-register-for-flood-warnings-as-hull-lags-behind-other-yorkshire-cities/> last accessed 11 April 2023.

⁴ G. Giannachi, Representing, Performing and Mitigating Climate Change in Contemporary Art Practice, *Leonardo* 45, 2 (2012) 124—131; C. Aragon, J. Buxton and E. Infield, The role of landscape installations in climate change communication, *Landscape and Urban Planning* 189 (2019) 11—14; Z. Altinay, Visual Communication of Climate Change: Local Framing and Place Attachment, *Coastal Management* 45, 4 (2017) 293—309.

⁵ L. McEwen, L. Gorell Barnes, K. Phillips and I. Biggs, Reweaving urban water-community relations: Creative, participatory river ‘daylighting’ and local hydrocitizenship, *Transactions of*

work, including by geographers, has focused on climate communication and the role of arts and humanities-led storytelling in engaging people in climate narratives.⁶ Far less has been said about arts for anticipatory climate action, and there are few large-scale studies evaluating the effectiveness of these approaches in driving behavioural change or building climate or flood resilience.⁷ Moreover, the potential of place-based, *historically-informed* approaches to drive action for climate empowerment has not – as yet – been adequately interrogated, and this despite the fact that city planners and global policy makers interested in nature-based and ‘slow water’ solutions are increasingly drawing on past water management practices as models for contemporary schemes.⁸ Crucially, none of these projects have made explicit use of pre-*twentieth* century histories of living with water and flood in order to drive climate resilient actions today. Finally, while artistic works informed and inspired by the climate crisis are now common, arts and heritage approaches are not at present well integrated into policy toolkits for Action for Climate Empowerment (ACE). It is these research and policy gaps that Risky Cities addresses.

In this paper, we contend that place-based and historically-informed creative engagement provides a valuable mechanism for building climate awareness, action and resilience. Our approach on Risky Cities combines archival research into histories of living with water and

the Institute of British Geographers, 45 (2020) 779–801; S. Schweizer, S. Davis and J. Leigh Thompson, Changing the Conversation about Climate Change: A Theoretical Framework for Place-Based Climate Change Engagement, *Environmental Communication*, 7,1 (2013) 42.

⁶ M. Hulme, Meet the Humanities, *Nature Climate Change*, 1 (2011) 177–179; J. Corbett, and B. Clark, The arts and humanities in climate change engagement, in: H. von Storch, (Ed), *Oxford Research Encyclopaedia of Climate Science*. Oxford University Press, 2017, 1–17; R. Rice, S. Rebich-Hespanha, and H. Zhu, Communicating about Climate Change Through Art and Science, in: J. Pinto, R. Gutsche, and P. Prado (Eds), *Climate Change, Media & Culture: Critical Issues in Global Environmental Communication*, Emerald, 2019, 129–154; S. Daniels and G. Endfield, Narratives of climate change: introduction, *Journal of Historical Geography* 35 (2009) 215–222.

⁷ See M. Burke, D. Ockwell, and L. Whitmarsh, Participatory arts and affective engagement with climate change: The missing link in achieving climate compatible behaviour change?, *Global Environmental Change* 49 (2018) 95–105; L. Sommer, and C. Klöckner, Does activist art have the capacity to raise awareness in audiences? —A study on climate change art at the ArtCOP21 event in Paris, *Psychology of Aesthetics, Creativity, and the Arts* 15, 1 (2021) 60–75.

⁸ On slow water solutions, see E. Gies, *Water Always Wins: Thriving in an age of drought and deluge*, Chicago University Press, 2022.

flood in Hull and the surrounding areas with participatory and creative methods in order to co-create 'learning histories' that are used to engage people in climate and flood resilience actions. In doing so, it also builds on the work of historical geographers who have conducted archival research alongside community work, the gathering of oral histories and other participatory methodologies.⁹ Thus while inherently interdisciplinary, our approach nevertheless holds at its heart an historical geographical analysis of medieval and early modern Hull. In centring the pre modern histories and geographies our chosen case study region, we offer an important addition and corrective to the existing literature on arts and climate change.¹⁰

Pre modern Hull was not unique in being located in the critical green-blue zone between land and sea, but excellent historical sources mean we know more about when the town flooded, how flood risk was managed, and who governed and managed water than for other English and Scottish towns. Risky Cities drew on a range of archival, published and community materials including: medieval letters patent, extensive civic and court records, antiquarian histories, maps, and nineteenth and twentieth-century newspapers; literary analysis of flood fictions in poetry, plays and folklore; and watery stories and flood experiences shared by community participants. Collectively, these allowed the team to reconstruct a flood timeline for Hull – revealing a history of repeated flood events affecting the town and surrounding

⁹ D. DeLyser, Towards a participatory historical geography: archival interventions, volunteer service, and public outreach in research on early women pilots, *Journal of Historical Geography* 46 (2014) 93–98; C. DeSilvey, Salvage Memory: constellating material histories on a hardscrabble homestead, *Cultural Geographies* 14 (2007) 401-424.

¹⁰ On performance as a method to communicate flood risk, see S. Scott-Bottoms, and M. Roe, Who is a hydrocitizen? The use of dialogic arts methods as a research tool with water professionals in West Yorkshire, UK, *Local Environment* 25 (2019) 273–289; M. Roe, and S. Scott-Bottoms, Improvisation as method: Engaging hearts and minds in the landscape through creative practice, *Urban Forestry & Urban Greening* 47 (2020) 1-10; on applied theatre, participatory methods and climate justice, see A. Franks, Kinder cuts and passionate modesties: the complex ecology of the invitation in participatory research, *AREA* 47, 3 (2014) 237–245; on visual arts, see H. Hawkins and A. Kanngieser, Artful climate change communication: Overcoming abstractions, insensibilities, and distances, *WIREs Climate Change* 8, 5 (2017) 1-12; C. Aragon, J. Buxton, and E. Infield, The role of landscape installations in climate change communication, *Landscape and Urban planning* 189 (2019) 11–14. None of these studies have utilized pre modern historical geographies in their practice-led research.

areas in the seven centuries after its foundation in c. 1260 – and corpus of stories and experiences exploring people’s relationships with their watery environment over eight centuries. The stories that emerge from the archive are primarily ones of surviving and thriving, of adaption and mitigation, of ongoing maintenance of water infrastructure and careful water governance, of living more or less successfully with water over many generations, rather than of flood-related disruption, disaster and cataclysm. To put it another way, living with water and flood was an integral part of working and dwelling in the medieval, early modern and modern town – a collective experience that was generative of what we have called elsewhere a ‘living with water mentality’.¹¹ It is these histories, stories and experiences that we and our creative partners and commissioned artists drew on in our creative and participatory practice discussed in this paper.

Elsewhere, we have referred to these as ‘learning histories’, borrowing a term first developed at Massachusetts Institute of Technology in the mid-1990s as a way of reflecting on the past in order to drive organisation learning and transformation.¹² For us, learning histories are multiple, jointly told stories, necessarily collaborative and creative. They fold together past, present and future in productive ways, so as to learn from the past and the present and rethink the future. This folding together happens in two main ways. Firstly, in the sense that place-based histories and stories are mobilised in the creative engagement activities, where they act as a hook for conversations about living with water and future climate change, as well as provide potential models for rethinking our future relationships with water and flood. They also help make big narratives about global climate change locally meaningful and relevant – and thus drive anticipatory action and behavioural change (on which see below) – and provide opportunities to build community-led climate solutions. And secondly, in the sense that the conversations that took place in and around the engagement activities were

¹¹ B. McDonagh, H. Worthen, S. Mottram and S. Buxton-Hill, *Living with water in medieval and early modern Hull*, *Journal of Historical Geography* (Forthcoming). Our thanks too to Flavia Manieri for sharing material from her forthcoming thesis on experiences of flooding in twentieth-century Hull.

¹² G. Roth and H. Bradbury, *Learning History: An Action Research Practice in Support of Actionable Learning*, in: P. Reason and H. Bradbury (Eds), *The Sage Handbook of Action Research*, Sage, 2007, 350-356.

themselves generative of further watery stories and experiences which contributed to the corpus of knowledge, understanding and experience within the team, our participants and wider community about histories and futures of living with and alongside water and flood. In this sense, our learning histories approach can be usefully understood as a participatory research method and novel addition to the toolkit for building climate action, empowerment and resilience.

In the remainder of this paper, we reflect briefly on three related but distinct practice-based approaches to using these learning histories in creative and/or arts-led engagement for climate action, each involving different relationships with creative partners and community participants, and offering different opportunities for assessing the effectiveness of our interventions amongst participants and audiences. Thus, the first section explores large-scale public art as a tool for driving climate awareness and action, the second explores our community engagement programme, and the final section reflects on our experiences of co-creating a site-responsive performance for the United Nations climate conference with partners at the National Youth Theatre of Great Britain.

Large-scale public art

FloodLights consisted of three site-responsive, multimedia light and sound installations shown over four nights in October 2021 in Kingston-Upon-Hull, UK, and attended by an audience of ~11,000. The installations were created by artists and commissioned by arts and cultural development charity Absolutely Cultured in partnership with the University of Hull, the Living with Water Partnership and Yorkshire Water. The *FloodLights* project illuminated Hull's experiences of living with water, past, present, and future, utilising local histories, stories and landmarks to drive climate awareness and action. These included flood histories and climate futures, maritime identities, marine pollution, and watery myths and folklore. Specifically, the installations included: *Sinuous City*, an immersive flood experience by multimedia creative studio Limbic Cinema, poet Vicky Foster and composer Joe Acheson (Hidden Orchestra) at 51 Whitefriargate (Figure x); *Sirens*, by Davy & Kirsten McGuire which used holographic projections into the water at Princes Quay Dock to display a variety of uncanny sea creatures, including mermaids, turtles and exotic fish alongside an encounter

with plastic pollution and climate change (Figure x); and *Overflow*, by Vent Media (Barret Hodgson) at the Trinity House Academy, which utilised the unique architectural design of the building as the canvas through which to explore the school's nautical connections and the city's sea-faring past (Figure x). Each of the installations was free and open for the general public to explore. The installations were accompanied by a digital programme of free behind-the-scenes videos, alongside a live roundtable discussion and launch event.

Development work on the project started in winter 2019/2020 with creative workshops involving University of Hull students, artists, community members and children and young people from Trinity House Academy. Team members led discussions about experiences of living with water in the city from the medieval to the modern period, as well as on climate change, sirens, folklore, and maritime history. There were also creative elements built into the process to prompt discussion: for example, using copies of historic maps to make memory boxes in which to imaginatively store participants' experiences of living with water. These workshops were recorded and transcribed, and the materials shared with artists later commissioned by Absolutely Cultured to produce the final three artworks, much delayed by Covid and eventually shown in the city in autumn 2021. Despite these delays, the workshops were able to facilitate a co-creative process which brought together the local community, artists and project partners in a way which enabled the sharing of experiences, ideas and knowledge that shaped each of the final artworks.

As our audience survey (n = 470) demonstrated, *FloodLights* facilitated audiences to engage in climate and water action, impacting audience thinking on climate change, flood risk and living with water and driving reported behavioural change amongst audience members (Smith et al., in review). Sixty-four per cent of respondents reporting that the event made them think about climate futures and a third reporting behavioural changes they planned to make in relation to this.¹³ Each of the three installations responded to place and site in different ways. *Overflow* engaged specifically with the historical maritime legacy of the city's built environment, while *Sinuous City* led participants to immersive and personal experiences of

¹³ Based on 457 survey responses.

flooding, and *Sirens* visualised imaginative aquatic entanglements between water and environment. Our survey demonstrates that each of these place-based approaches – especially the site-responsive installations which mobilised Hull’s watery histories and identities – were crucial in generating engagement and action towards climate resilience. As a form of place-based historically-informed arts-led engagement *FloodLights* provided opportunities to make global narratives tangible at the local scale – and hence prompt climate action and behavioural change.

Creative community engagement

Similar experiences were reported in our creative community engagement programme which took place in summer and autumn 2022. This revolved around a series of co-created community textile, poetry and zine workshops, attended by sixty-three residents from Cottingham, Preston Road and Boothferry Road, all areas of the city affected by floods in the last two decades. Similar to *FloodLights*, the workshops utilised a two-way sharing process whereby the project team shared ‘learning histories’ through maps, images and archival materials and community members were invited to contribute their own lived experiences, photos and flood memories. Participants were then invited to respond and reflect upon these histories through creative practice, facilitated by practitioners who provided tools, materials and learning to support participants to embroider, weave, draw, paint or produce poems and creative writing. The resulting creative materials layered together elements of Hull’s watery history with participants’ memories, stories or reflections (see figure x).

Creative outputs from the workshops were shared via a further series of arts-led events, which sought to continue the legacy of the workshops beyond the creative ‘doings’ and formed part of the ongoing dialogue and knowledge exchange between researchers, workshop members and wider community audiences. The textile workshops, for example, culminated in the ‘Follow the Thread Exhibition’, which toured the Hull between August and October 2022 attracting almost 1000 visitors; while five commissioned artists responded to the creative writing portfolio produced at community workshops, while the art workshops generated a flood resilience zine titled ‘Wet Feet, Warm Hearts, Strong Places’, which shares participants creative work alongside practical flood resilience advice. It will shortly be

circulated to over 4000 homes within and beyond the wards in which the project worked. The poetry from the creative writing workshops was used as part of a 'writing pack' which informed a series of five artistic commissions shared at live performances attended by 146 people and featuring music, poetry and spoken word, digital animations, visual arts, and a community story map.

Evaluations of the programme were undertaken via focus groups with workshop participants, interviews with artists, and feedback surveys. These evidence the significant impacts of the programme, including the value many participants placed on having space to discuss their experiences of and feelings about flooding, especially the 2007 floods. This was not a topic broached by the project team, but rather an opportunity embraced by participants who typically led the discussions, interweaving their own memories and experiences with pre modern Hull's watery history. In several cases, living memory became productively entangled with the archival materials, where twentieth-century newspaper headlines provided points of recollection for those who grew up in the city in the 1960s and 1970s. In addition, our evaluations demonstrate increased community awareness that the city had always been 'watery'; that is, subject to repeated flood events, some of them problematic for local communities but on other occasions, treated in a fairly mundane manner in the historical record. This knowledge provided a prompt for participants to reflect on and share how future climate change and flooding might affect them. Many participants connected this awareness with action: for example, choosing to check their own flood risk, cascade conversations by talking to family members about historical and recent examples of flooding, and sign up for national flood alerts. Put simply, the project's creative community programme encouraged multi-faceted engagement with Hull's flood and climate history that offered participants opportunities to better understand, adapt and respond to future environmental change. This impact extended beyond community participants to include the project's commissioned artists who told us that their working practices and creative foci would change as a result of their involvement in Risky Cities, and to the project's researchers, whose commitment to engaging with community participants meant that research outcomes were immediately and profoundly tangible. Thus, we have found that place-based and historically-informed arts engagement is a powerful tool not only for engaging with community histories, but also for

facilitating and empowering individuals and communities to understand, adapt and respond to environmental change.¹⁴

Youth-led theatre and performance

On the Edge was a collaborative project between the National Youth Theatre (NYT) and the University of Hull funded by a UK Climate Resilience Programme impact award and part of the MELT partnership, a multi-year creative response to the climate crisis. The co-created and site-responsive theatrical performance platformed young people's experiences of living with climate change in UK coastal and estuarine communities on a global policy stage – in the Green Zone at United Nations Climate Change Conference (COP26) in Glasgow, UK, in November 2021. The co-creative process was characterised by an intensive two-way dialogue between academic researchers and young creatives aged 18-26 facilitated via online development workshops featuring an initial cast of 200 young people from across the UK and in person rehearsals, a live preview performance and Q&A session at the NYT's Production House the week before COP as part of the Islington Green Festival. The final 90-minute performance premiered a new play, *I Don't Care*, written and directed by Adeola Yemitan and devised by the NYT Company in collaboration with members of the Risky Cities team. The play explored young people's agency to manage the competing challenges of flood risk, coastal change, high socio-economic deprivation, and unemployment, and to identify solutions, negotiate barriers to action and build resilience in a changing climate future. *I Don't Care* was followed by a climate cabaret directed by Tatty Hennessey using spoken word, poetry, music and magic to explore an intergenerational conversation about climate change in coastal areas. The live performance elements were interspersed with a number of short films, and the event concluded with a round table discussion with participants reflecting on the process of working collaboratively on the project.

¹⁴ See also: S. MacKinnon, *Practising community-based participatory research: Stories of engagement, empowerment, and mobilization*, UBC Press, 2018, 48; L.M Vaughn, and F. Jacquez, Participatory Research Methods – Choice Points in the Research Process, *Journal of Participatory Research Methods* 1, 1 (2020) 1–13.

Evaluation of the project was undertaken in two principle ways. Reflective journals kept by participants – including the academic researchers – chart the cognitive, bodily, and emotional experiences of those involved which ultimately challenged our collective expectations about young people’s experiences of the climate crisis. Participants reported their anxiety about climate change, alongside anger and frustration around a lack of government action in addressing climate impacts. This was coupled with a concern for the intersectional challenges faced by young people who are dealing with not just a climate crisis, but also rising inequality, racism, and long-term economic adversity. Hope was a repeated theme in the journals, as were reflections on the value of artistic and creative practice in addressing the climate crisis:

Art isn’t problem solving.
Art is sitting in our emotions
holding space for complication
bearing witness
collective wrangling with
complexity

Activism through art is empowerment to me. And I hope, above all else, young people saw it or listened and felt seen and heard.

A small audience survey (n = 27) was also conducted. Ninety-seven per cent of respondents rated their experience of *On the Edge* good or very good, with audience members reporting a range of emotional responses to the performance from frustration at a sense of time running out, sadness, resignation and rage through to joy, amusement, hope and a feeling of being motivated to action. More than two-thirds of the audience identified specific ways that their thinking in relation to young people, flooding and climate change had been changed: for example, by underlining our collective vulnerability in the face of climate change, by highlighting the depth and complexity of young people’s responses to the climate crisis, and by spotlighting issues of class, race and the difficulties of activism as a priority in everyday life. Several respondents referred to the local as a mechanism for underlining the urgency of the climate crises, noting that the play ‘makes [flooding] more local – makes it more real’ and

'brought it home even more'. Crucially, 88 per cent of respondents also reported that as a result of watching *On the Edge*, they planned to change their own advocacy or actions in relation to young people, flooding and climate change. Example actions included:

I'm going to go to as many protests as I can. I can't make excuses anymore

I will definitely be talking to more family/friends about how we all get involved and make changes in our lives

Has definitely inspired me to use theatre/engage with theatre projects as a way to create awareness

More than 3,500 people also watched the livestream events including the UK Climate Resilience showcase in Hull in October 2022, where the audience was visibly moved to tears. In summary then, much like *FloodLights*, *On the Edge* drove cognitive shifts amongst its participants and audience, empowering individuals to engage in climate and water action.

Conclusions

In conclusion, the practice-based elements of the Risky Cities programme underline the effectiveness of place-based, historically-informed creative community engagement in driving cognitive shifts and behavioural change amongst both participants and audiences in relation to climate issues. Our participatory and creative 'learning histories' approach offers crucial opportunities to make big global narratives about climate change relatable and meaningful at the local level – and so drive anticipatory climate action. Our quantitative and qualitative data strongly bears this out, and provides the first large-scale analyses of how pre modern histories and geographies can be mobilized to drive climate action and behavioural change across a range of scales from co-created community engagement activities to large-scale public arts. Crucially, our approach provides scalable solutions to building awareness, action and resilience in other UK and global cities in the face of the climate emergency. We hope others will take up the challenge and provocation.

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